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ANATOMICAL AND TOPOGRAPHICAL STRUCTURE OF THE EXTRAHEPATIC BILE DUCT IN EXPERIMENTAL ANIMALS

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ABSTRACT

The article studies the variants of formation of external bile ducts of the liver in rats and the features of their anatomical structure. Since rats do not have a gallbladder, the right and left hepatic bile ducts merge, and the common hepatic bile duct flows into the posterior wall of the duodenum.

Keywords: rat, liver, bile duct, duodenum, common bile duct.

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АНАТОМО-ТОПОГРАФИЧЕСКОЕ СТРОЕНИЕ ВНЕПЕЧЕНОЧНОГО ЖЕЛЧНОГО ПРОТОКА У ЭКСПЕРИМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ЖИВОТНЫХ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье изучаются варианты формирования наружных желчных протоков печени у крыс и особенности их анатомического строения. Поскольку у крыс отсутствует желчный пузырь, правый и левый печеночные желчные протоки сливаются и общий печеночный желчный проток впадает в заднюю стенку двенадцатиперстной кишки.

Ключевые слова: крыса, печень, желчный проток, двенадцатиперстная кишка, общий желчный проток.

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TAJRIBA HAYVONLARIDA JIGARDAN TASHQI O'T YO'LLARINING ANATOMO-TOPOGRAFIK TUZILISHI

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada kalamushlarda jigardan tashqi o't yo'llarining hosil bo'lish variantlari va anatomik tuzilishining xususiyatlari o'rganilgan. Kalamushlarda o't pufagi yo'qligi sababli o'ng va chap jigar o't yo'llari qo'shilib umumiy jigar o't yo'li o'n ikki barmoqli ichakka tushuvch qismining orqa devoriga quyuladi.

Kalit so'zlar: kalamush, jigar, o't yo'llari, o'n ikki barmoqli ichak, umumiy o't yo'li.

Kirish. So'ngi yillardagi ilmiy adabiyotlarni tahlil qilganimizda kalamushlarda jigardan tashqi o't yo'llarining anatomo-topografik tuzilish va o't yo'llarining hosil bo'lish variantlari haqidagi ma'lumotlar uchratmadik. Ayrim mualliflar quyvon va kalamushlarda jigardan tashqi o't yo'llarining gistologik tuzilishini qiyosiy taqoslab keltirgan[1,3]. Bazi olimlar o't yo'llarining adrenergic va holinergik nerv tolalarining gistologik tuzilishni o'rgangan[2,5]. Adabiyotlardagi ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, butun dunyo bo'ylab xoletsistit bilan kasallanish yildan-yilga o'sib bormoqda va u bilan bog'liq xoletsistektomiya operatsiyalar soni ham o'sib bormoqda. Binobarin, o't pufagi bo'lgan va bo'lmagan sutemizuvchilarda jigardan tashqari o't yo'llarining hosil bo'lish variantlarini qiyosiy o'rganish hamda xoletsistektomiyadan so'ng jigardan tashqari o't yo'llarining strukturaviy qayta tashkil etilishi nazariy va amaliy tibbiyotning dolzarb ilmiy muammosi hisoblanadi [4].

Tadqiqotning maqsadi va vazifalari. Kalamushlarda jigardan tashqi o't yo'llarining hosil bo'lish variantlarini o'rganish.

Materiallar va tadqiqot usullari. Bizning tadqiqotimiz uchun 12 ta kalamushdan olingan jigar, jigardan tashqi o't yo'llari va o'n ikki barmoqli ichakning organokomplekslari olindi. Hayvonlar natriy etaminal anesteziyasi ta'sirida qon chiqarish (qorin aortasini kesish) yo'li bilan o'ldirildi. Organlar neytral formalinning 12% li eritmasida qotirildi. Anatomik preparovka usulidan foydalanib, MBS-2 binokulyar mikroskopida (okulyr - 8, ob'ektiv - 0,6) sun'iy yoritilgan holda jigardan tashqi o't yo'llarining hosil bo'lish variantlari va qopqa venasiga nisbatan jiylashish topografiyasi o'rganildi. Olingan natijalarga statistik ishlov berish amalga oshirildi.

Natijalar va muhokama. Kalamushlar - o't pufagi bo'lmagan sutemizuvchilar oilasiga mansub. Biz Jigardan tashqi o't yo'llarining hosil bo'lish variantlarini, qopqa venasiga nisbatav anatomo-topografik joylashish variantlari aniqlandi[1-rasm].

1-rasm. O'ng (1) va chap (2) jigar yo'llari o'tkir burchak ostida qo'shilib, umumiy jigar yo'lini (3) hosil qiladi, u oshqozon osti bezi (4) parenximasidan o'tib, o'n ikki barmoqli ichakka (5) quyuladi. Qopqa venasi (6) o'ngda va pastda joylashgan. MBS-2 mikroskop ostida tekshirildi. Kattalashtirilgan. 8x1.

1- rasmda tasvirlanganidek o'ng va chap jigar bo'laklaridan chiqan jigarning xususiy o't yo'llari 90° burchak hosil qilib qo'shiladi va jigarning umumiy o't yo'lini hosil qiladi. O't pufagi

yo`qligi uchun jigarning umumiy o`t yo`li to`g`ridan-to`g`ri o`n ikki barmoqli ichakning tushuvchi qismini orqa devoriga borib quyiladi. Bazi xollarda jigarning xususiy o`t yo`llari qo`shilmasdan to`g`ti borib, o`n ikki ichak devoriga kirganda qo`shiladi. Qopqa venasi o`t yo`liga nisbatan o`ngda va pasda joylashadi. Jigarning umumiy o`t yo`li ko`p xollarda m`eda osti bezi parenximasining ichidan o`tadi. Bazi xollarda uning orqa yuzasidan yoki oldingi yuzasida joylashadi[2-rasm].

2-rasm. Kalamushda oshqozon osti bezi parenximasida (1) umumiy o't yo'li (2) ko'rinadi, u darvoza venasining (3) oldida va chap tomonida joylashgan. MBS-2 mikroskop ostida tekshirildi. Kattalashtirilgan. 8x1.

Mikroskopda maxsus okulyar lineyka yordamida jigardan tashqi o`t yo`llarining uzunligi va diametri o`lchanganda quyidagi m`alumatlar aniqlandi; Jigarning chap xususiy o`t yo`lining o`rtacha uzunligi $2,3 \pm 0,1$ mm, diametri $0,5 \pm 0,02$ mm ni tashkil qiladi. Jigarning o`ng xususiy o`t yo`lining o`rtach uzunligi $2,5 \pm 0,1$ mm ni, diametri $0,5 \pm 0,02$ mm ni hosil qildi. Jigar umumiy o`t yo`lining o`rtacha uzunligi $12,5 \pm 0,2$ mm ni, diametri $1,1 \pm 0,2$ mm ni tashkil qiladi[3-rasm].

3-rasm. O'ng (1) va chap (2) jigar o't yo'llari o'tkir burchak ostida qo'shilib, umumiy jigar yo'lini (3) hosil qiladi, darvoza venasining (4) oldida va o'ng tomonida joylashgan. MBS-2 mikroskop ostida tekshirildi. Kattalashtirilgan 8x1.

Xulosa. Shunday qilib, kalamushlarda o`t pufagining tabiiy holda bo`lmasligi ularda jigardan tashqi o`t yo`llarining anatomo-topografik tuzilish o`t xaltasi bo`lgan sutemizuvch xayvonlardan

anch farq qiladi. O't yo'llarining uzunlugu va diametri jihatdan nisbatan katta ko'rsatgichga ega bo'lish ma'lum jixatdan o't pufagi vazifasini bajaradi.

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10 ЖИЛД, 1 СОН

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